

IHI Project ID - SYNTHIA

Synthetic Data Generation Framework for Integrated Validation

WP1 – Strategy, coordination and project management

D1.1-2024

Project Management Tool and Handbook

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Document History

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V0.2	27/9/2024	Version 0.2 includes the comments of the PMO
V0.3	30/9/2024	Version 0.3 feedback round from PMO, and update on comments &
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V1.1	16/10/2024	Version 1.1 Inclusion of CHUV (29) NICE (30) associated partner in partner list (administrative error)
V1.2	29/10/2024	Version 1.2 Comments IHI PO addressed in deliverable
V2.0	30/10/2024	Version 2.0 Final Version for IHI submission

1 Executive Summary

This handbook is meant to give guiding information to navigate through the project and provide a set of principles in an understandable way, explaining structure, tasks, decision making processes, and responsibilities at all levels of project execution.

All information and general principles are based on the Grant Agreement, the Description of the Action and the Consortium Agreement. In addition to all the above, this handbook is based on experience, project management standards and best practices.

The main stakeholder responsible for keeping the information up to date is the Project Management Office, which will be done upon need, such as amendments to the Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, or significant changes to the organization of the work in the consortium, requiring a different approach to the project management.

1 Executive Summary	2
2 Introduction.....	4
2.1 Abbreviations.....	5
2.2 Definitions.....	6
2.3 Code of Conduct.....	7
3 Methods	8
3.1 Project Overview	8
3.1.1 Project summary	8
3.1.2 Participants in the SYNTHIA Consortium	8
3.1.3 Project Objectives	9
3.1.4 Governance structure	10
3.2 Processes.....	12
3.2.1 Internal Communication	12
3.2.2 Internal Communication Tools	14
3.2.3 External Communication	15
3.2.4 Risk Management	15
3.2.5 Deliverable preparation, review and approval	16
3.2.6 Deliverables content review:	17
3.2.7 Project Change Management	18
3.3 Reports Overview	19
3.3.1 Reportings overview	20
3.3.2 Eligible cost	21
3.3.3 Certificates on the Financial Statement	22
4 Results.....	23
5 Discussion	23
6 Conclusion	23
7 Repository for primary data	23

2 Introduction

The project handbook aims to provide an overview of the management and administrative procedures and principles that will guarantee an efficient execution of the Synthia Project. Aiming at high-quality project results, special attention will be paid to ensure that project results are delivered in due time, within budget and considering the formal requirements and standards of the project.

The main objective of this handbook is to set out the principles of the project in an understandable way, explaining structure, tasks, decision making processes, and responsibilities at all levels of project execution. All information and general principles are based on the Grant Agreement, the Description of the Action, and the Consortium Agreement. In addition to all the above, this handbook is based on experience, project management standards and best practices.

The scope of the project handbook is to be a guidance document. As a result, it does not have any impact on legal assessment, for which participants should always refer to the Grant Agreement (including its Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

In case of discrepancies between the project handbook, Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement, the Grant Agreement always prevails.

The handbook is updated when need arises, to ensure that content and evolution of the project are reflected.

The established procedures are based on the code of conduct, general principles, and policies set up in the guidelines of the IHI program. These function as the starting point of any interpretation and the procedures and principles of management are based on the PM2 methodology, internationally recognized, with the main chapters considered:

- Project overview
- Processes
- Reports overview

2.1 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
AC	Associated Collaborator
AE	Affiliated Entity
AMGA	Annotated Model Grant Agreement
AP	Associated Partner
BEN	Beneficiary
CO	Coordinator
DoA	Description of the Action
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EXCOM	Executive Committee
GA	General Assembly
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IP	Intellectual Property
PMO	Project Management Office - SYNTHIA
STEERCO	Steering Committee
UC	Use Case
WP	Work package
WPL	Work Package Leader

2.2 Definitions

- **Beneficiary:** Wording used in most of the legal documents. Legal entity who has signed the Grant Agreement with IHI or the Form of Accession to the GA.
- **Consortium:** The SYNTHIA Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
- **Consortium Agreement:** Agreement concluded amongst SYNTHIA participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement, which will prevail.
- **Deliverable review:** An evaluation procedure by one or more reviewers, which precedes the distribution of a deliverable (as defined in the Work plan) to the IHI.
- **Grant Agreement.** The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI JU for the undertaking of the SYNTHIA project, with agreement nr. 101172872
- **Participant.** Organisation who has signed the SYNTHIA Grant Agreement.
- **Partner.** Organisation who has signed the Grant Agreement with IHI or the Form of Accession (see also Participant or Beneficiary).
- **Personal information** includes general information about an individual such as name, home address, email and IP address and other contact details. It also includes more sensitive personal information that may be subject to additional specialized legal or contractual obligations such as financial records, government issued identification numbers, medical records, educational or employment records, sexual orientation, race, family status and political or religious affiliations.
- **Project.** The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes.
- **Quality assurance.** All the planned and systematic activities implemented to provide adequate confidence that an entity will fulfil requirements for quality.
- **Quality policy.** A set of principles on which quality assurance procedures are based.
- **Risk.** Uncertainty that may have a significant impact on the execution or outcome of the project, and which effect may be negative – a threat risk - or positive – an opportunity risk.
- **Work plan.** Schedule of tasks, deliverables, efforts, dates and responsibilities corresponding to the work to be carried out, as specified in Annex I to the Grant Agreement.

2.3 Code of Conduct

We show our commitment We all show commitment by acknowledging that we've read, understood and agreed the terms and conditions of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

Speak up, report concerns. If you have an **ethics concern** or suspect that someone is behaving illegally or unethically, please speak up. Talk to your work package leader, reach out to the PMO, or members of the Executive Committee.

The consortium does **not tolerate retaliation** against anyone who initiates or participates in the ethics process, asks questions or raises concerns in good faith. All members and leaders are required to cooperate and be truthful.

Virtually every country regulates the collection, use, storage, disclosure, deletion and transfer of personal information. When accessing or handling personal information, we must **comply with applicable laws and regulations**, contractual obligations of handling Personal Information.

We are **intentional and careful with Personal Information**: We use only responsible and lawful means to access, collect, use, share, transfer or store the personal information of others, and use personal information solely for legitimate purposes related to the project.

We treat everyone — team members, stakeholders — with **dignity and respect**. We must all be able to do our jobs in a safe and respectful environment without the distractions and disruptions caused by offensive, unprofessional or inappropriate behaviour in the workplace.

Before you disclose or distribute any **confidential information**, project management approval must be obtained, and the appropriate terms of use established.

We **travel and report expenses** responsibly as good guardians of (public) funds.

3 Methods

3.1 Project Overview

3.1.1 Project summary

Project acronym:	SYNTHIA
Project title:	Synthetic Data Generation Framework for Integrated validation
Grant Agreement number:	101172872
IHI call topic:	Maximizing the potential of synthetic data generation in healthcare applications (HORIZON-JU-IHI-2023-05-04)
Project start date:	1 st of September 2024
Project End date:	31 st of August 2029
Duration of the Action:	60 months
Number of participants:	28 Beneficiaries, 5 Affiliated Entities, 6 Associated Partners
Total project costs (included non-EU funded):	€ 22,415,540.00
Requested EU Contribution (IHI funding):	€ 12,438,775.00

3.1.2 Participants in the SYNTHIA Consortium

1	CO	IISLAFE	FUNDACION PARA LA INVESTIGACION DEL HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARIO LA FE DE LA COMUNIDAD VALENCIANA	ES	995991539
2	BEN	BSC	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	ES	999655520
3	BEN	LUMC	ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN	NL	999990849
4	BEN	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	IT	999993953
4.1	AE	IRCCS-S	AZIENDA UNITA' SANITARIA LOCALE DI BOLOGNA	IT	951425568
4.2	AE	IRCCS-A	IRCCS AZIENDA OSPEDALIERO-UNIVERSITARIA DI BOLOGNA	IT	991016991
5	BEN	PATVO	PATVOCATES GMBH	DE	937524886
6	BEN	MAT	MATICAL INNOVATION SL	ES	908013994
7	BEN	CHA	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN BERLIN	DE	999992692
8	BEN	HUS	HUS-YHTYMA	FI	999483830
9	BEN	ICH	HUMANITAS MIRASOLE SPA	IT	999785015
10	BEN	TRAIN	TRAIN SRL	IT	879901357

11	BEN	UPM	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES	999974844
12	BEN	CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	EL	998802502
13	BEN	EMBL	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	DE	999988230
14	BEN	ITTM	INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE (ITTM) SA	LU	920738745
15	BEN	i-HD	THE EUROPEAN INSTITUTE FOR INNOVATION THROUGH HEALTH DATA	BE	923112723
16	BEN	ERASMUS	ERASMUS UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM ROTTERDAM	NL	999988424
17	BEN	UNIVIE	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	AT	999866883
18	BEN	FRAUNHOFER	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	DE	999984059
19	BEN	VHIO	FUNDACIO PRIVADA INSTITUT D'INVESTIGACIO ONCOLOGICA DE VALL-HEBRON (VHIO)	ES	995163935
20	BEN	VHIR	FUNDACIO HOSPITAL UNIVERSITARI VALL D'HEBRON - INSTITUT DE RECERCA	ES	999541642
21	BEN	EAPM	European Alliance for Personalised Medicine	SI	889456245
22	BEN	DNV	DNV AS	NO	999929060
23	BEN	PFIZER	PFIZER INC	US	887211374
24	BEN	GEHC	GE MEDICAL SYSTEMS SCS	FR	994075886
24.1	AE	GEHC-DE	GE HEALTHCARE GMBH	DE	884276251
24.2	AE	GEHC-HU	GE HEALTHCARE MAGYARORSZAG KFT	HU	896662666
24.3	AE	GEHC-ES	GENERAL ELECTRIC HEALTHCARE ESPANA SA	ES	904586790
25	BEN	JANSSSEN	JANSSSEN PHARMACEUTICA NV	BE	998398206
26	BEN	GV	GATES VENTURES LLC	US	891302931
27	BEN	NOVO	NOVO NORDISK A/S	DK	999940021
28	BEN	BMS	BRISTOL-MYERS SQUIBB COMPANY CORP	US	994864011
29	AP	CHUV	CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE VAUDOIS	CH	999600909
30	AP	NICE	NATIONAL INSTITUT FOR HEALTH AND CARE EXCELLENCE	UK	984454262

3.1.3 Project Objectives

The overall objective is to guarantee a high-quality project implementation according to the work plan and within budgeted costs and to ensure that the scientific activities are managed efficiently. The workplan **objectives** are the following:

Objective 1) A thorough understanding of the requirements for SD in a set of relevant healthcare use cases, which are representative of key application areas, and relevant to showcase and establish the broad generalisability of the proposed SDG methods.

Objective 2) Establish SDG methods and tools (new and enhanced) that reflect and propel state of the art, offered to the field to utilise and to build on as further advances arise.

Objective 3) Establish a comprehensive framework for SD evaluation, encompassing data and privacy protection, bias characterisation and minimisation, data quality fitness for purpose assessments. These will be achieved through a combination of data protection by design and default, well-documented and established methodologies, and statistical tools, and inputs to standardisation.

Objective 4) Validate the utility of SD in various healthcare applications, including the development of AI-based tools for diagnosis and prognosis (solid tumours and AD), the use of synthetic control arms in new treatment evaluation (AD and haematological malignancies), and the evaluation of digital biomarkers from non-invasive devices (T2DM).

Objective 5) Ensure access to the SD as a reusable collection of datasets to be used in the project and made available as open or controlled access research data, to the wider community.

Objective 6) Contribute to the cohesion of public and private entities, and the visibility of a joint community of SD generators and SD users, sharing insights, good practices and evidence of the value from SD. This community will also surface new requirements and new opportunities for SD.

3.1.4 Governance structure

The governance structure of SYNTHIA has been elaborated to respond to the needs of the project, its size and its complexity. An effective managerial structure will ensure a fair governance of the project and facilitate an agile implementation. Its main bodies, which are conveniently described in both the GA and CA, are schematically presented in figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Synthia Governing Bodies

Synthia will adopt a classic project governance model that will require active involvement of both private and public stakeholders. The management structure is developed to respond to the international large-scale multi-stakeholder character of the project.

Figure 2: infographic capturing the project structure

3.2 Processes

3.2.1 Internal Communication

All work packages and use cases have been assigned mailing lists (to be consulted in the SharePoint) based on the inventory among partners about their involvement in the project. The outreach inside the consortium is expected from the work package leaders with support from the project management office.

Project Management Office

The PMO is in charge of the day-to-day overview of the project, safeguarding adherence to planning and collaborating with the different governance bodies by facilitating meetings, tools and templates for the tasks carried out in the work packages (WPs) and use cases (UCs).

Workpackage Internal communication

Work packages are organized according to the Description of Action (DoA), and WP leaders, both the Academic and Industry leads are expected to set out the lines of their work package and engage all its members for their contributions. The Steering Committee (SteerCo) meetings are the forum for work package leaders to communicate on a regular basis the WP progress reporting.

Use Cases

The UCs are the disease specific target areas of SYNTHIA, each use case has both an academic and industry leads, which are expected to work with work package leaders. The UCs Leads are part of the Extended SteerCo, which serves as their forum for progress reporting.

	<i>ExCom</i>	<i>SteerCo</i>	<i>PMO</i>	<i>WP lead</i>	<i>UC Lead</i>
<i>IISLAFE</i>	X	X	X	X	X
<i>BSC</i>		X		X	
<i>LUMC</i>					
<i>UNIBO</i>					X
<i>IRCCS-S</i>					X
<i>IRCCS-A</i>					X
<i>PATVO</i>					
<i>MAT</i>	X	X	X	X	
<i>CHA</i>		X		X	
<i>HUS</i>					X
<i>ICH</i>		X		X	

	<i>ExCom</i>	<i>SteerCo</i>	<i>PMO</i>	<i>WP lead</i>	<i>UC Lead</i>
<i>TRAIN</i>					
<i>UPM</i>		X		X	
<i>CERTH</i>					
<i>EMBL</i>					
<i>ITTM</i>					
<i>i-HD</i>		X		X	
<i>ERASMUS</i>					
<i>UNIVIE</i>		X		X	
<i>FRAUNHOFER</i>	X	X			X
<i>VHIO</i>					X
<i>VHIR</i>					
<i>EAPM</i>					
<i>DNV</i>					
<i>PFIZER</i>	X	X		X	X
<i>GEHC</i>	X	x		X	X
<i>GEHC-DE</i>	X	X		X	X
<i>GEHC-HU</i>	X	X		X	X
<i>GEHC-ES</i>	X	X		X	X
<i>JANSSEN</i>		X		X	X
<i>GV</i>	X	X		X	X
<i>NOVO</i>		X		X	X
<i>BMS</i>		X		X	
<i>CHUV</i>					
<i>NICE</i>		X		X	

3.2.2 Internal Communication Tools

E-mail

To ensure that communications within the project complies with the principles listed above, the Consortium will adopt the following approach in that respect:

- Use of electronic mail as the main tool for communication within the Consortium, preferably corporate email.
- Documentation of discussions, agreements and decisions made by phone is encouraged. Specifically, phone conferences should always have agenda and minutes, for which a template is available in SharePoint.
- Several distribution lists have been initially created which can be used by any participant depending on the subject of the message. Additional lists may be created as the project evolves, if necessary, the Project Management Office will be responsible for updating the above-mentioned lists with the information received from Participants.

When a list is used, care should be taken by Participants to use the “reply to all” feature only when relevant. The table below shows the distribution lists created by the time of publishing this Handbook. The list will be amended and extended throughout the course of this project:

Purpose	email
Executive Committee	synthia_excom@iislafe.es
Steering Committee	synthia_sc@iislafe.es
Project Management Office	synthia_office@iislafe.es
Outgoing Communication	community@ihi-synthia.eu
<i>(do not reply)</i>	

WP & UC specific Mailing lists.

SharePoint

Microsoft SharePoint has been chosen and created for SYNTHIA for the purpose of project repository for relevant information. The tool facilitates the exchange of documents within the Consortium (i.e. meeting minutes, documents in progress, final versions and other relevant reports or announcements).

The SharePoint platform also provides the possibility to publish meetings and events, work simultaneously in channels, documents and uploading files at Project and WP-level. All Beneficiaries, Affiliated Entities and Associated Partners of the SYNTHIA project are granted access to the SharePoint from MATICAL. Changes to the SharePoint are managed by the PMO.

3.2.3 External Communication

SYNTHIA external communication and policy activities will be centered on increasing general awareness of the project itself, on the generation and use of synthetic data in the disease areas of the six defined use cases and on fostering connections. An additional set of activities will be set up to develop learning paths and offer trainings.

Disseminating digital content and create online engagement will be the main pathway to reach out, however face-to-face interactions and dedicated content are also envisioned.

Figure 3 below showcases the SYNTHIA internal community and the stakeholders we aim to target.

Figure 3: SYNTHIA internal community and stakeholders

- Online: Website, newsletters and social media campaigns, mailings
- Face-to-face: Conference participations, planned meetings
- Content: Informative blogs, videos, infographics, PPT presentations, press releases, folders.

3.2.4 Risk Management

Risks are inherent in any activity, but close monitoring of the work plan in cooperation with the WP and UC leaders will enable the early identification of bottlenecks, risks or delays, prompting the initiation of appropriate contingency planning. The early identification of risks will lead to timely adjustments to the work plan through corrective actions as needed.

The project risk table will be continuously updated to incorporate any additional risks that emerge during project execution, with specific assignments to one or more WPs. A relevance index will be built using a simplified system of two variables (impact, probability), each of them measured on a three-point scale (1-Low, 2-Medium, 3-High) to focus on the most relevant ones. The WP leaders will hold the responsibility to

identify the probability and/or impact of risks within their assigned WPs before they occur in order to implement a mitigation plan in cooperation with GEHC and MATICAL.

If a risk persists, the WP leaders will promptly alert the SteerCo to formulate additional mitigation strategies. If activation of a contingency plan becomes necessary, the most suitable plan will be proposed by the STEERCO for approval by the Executive Committee.

A risk registry with mitigation and contingency plans will be maintained and included in the periodic reports. The presence of risk increases dramatically when projects include a significant research component, due to its inherently exploratory nature and uncertain outcome.

Risk Management (led by MAT & GEHC)

The risk monitoring is a way to **identify, analyse, assess and monitor risks** affecting the project or its results, and the **development and monitoring of associated mitigation and contingency plans** that aim at minimising the potential negative effects (for **threat risks**) and maximising the potential benefits (for **opportunity risks**).

3.2.5 Deliverable preparation, review and approval

The deliverable review process is initiated by the PMO, who sends a request to the WPLs (and task leader if applicable) to whom the Deliverable or project document is assigned in the DoA. This reminder includes the expected timing and the IHI (SYNTHIA) template to be used for the deliverable.

The WP leader is in charge of follow-up with the progress of the deliverable and to make sure the deliverable is sent to the PMO by the specific deadline EOB. The quality check of the deliverable will be conducted, and comments from the SteerCo will be collected. Any delays or unforeseen issues will be reported to the PMO, with full explanation suitable to be communicated to the IHI Officer, if necessary.

Activities: Deliverables review – quality assurance

Day – 20: A first draft of the document is generated by the author(s) and submitted to the PMO within a minimum of 20 calendar days prior to the due date. A tracking document to follow-up on the process for each deliverable is published on the project’s shared repository (part of the project GANTT)

Day – 15: The PMO responds back to the authors of the deliverable with comments and aligns with the author to send the deliverable to the SteerCo.

Day – 7: The comments are processed by the author, who then presents the final version to the PMO.

Day –2: Final revision by Coordinator and PMO.

Due day: Submission in the Funding & Tenders Portal by the Coordinator.

Any review is done with “track changes”. The following paragraph serves as a reference for the review process to meet following quality criteria:

3.2.6 Deliverables content review:

- Adherence to IHI templates
- Completeness: Information must address all aspects related to the purpose of the document information. The deliverable should be complete and in line with the original specifications of the project, fulfilling the required criteria outlined in the DoA. Redundant information must be avoided, as it obscures the clarity of documents.
 - ❖ Related indicators: Missing content, Redundancy.
- Methodological accuracy and data integrity: Information contained in the document must be reliable and verifiable. This means that all background information used in the reports should be appropriately supported by references. Information on results should be sufficiently backed to avoid misinterpretation. The use of statistically validated objective data should be prioritised and adherence to methodological accuracy is required.
 - ❖ Related indicators: Error, Insufficient references/objective supporting data, Ambiguity.
- Accuracy on logic/writing/depth: All information should be provided to the depth needed for the purpose of the document.
 - ❖ Related indicators: Lacking details, Excessive details.

- Relevance: Information used in the document should focus on the key issues and be written in a manner that takes into consideration the target audience
 - ❖ Related indicators: Irrelevant information.

Regarding appearance and structure:

- Adherence to standards: it is important that documents are prepared with uniform appearance and structure so that, even if they are produced by different authors, they appear as originating from a single initiative (see deliverables template).
 - ❖ Related indicators: Lack of uniformity in presentation.
- WP leads: Before submitting the first draft to the PMO, it is recommended to align content and completeness on WP-level with the WP Leads, to make sure that there are no constraints regarding confidentiality, incomplete or unsuitable content.
 - ❖ Related indicators: Alignment on content and suitability on WP level

3.2.7 Project Change Management

The Grant Agreement can and must be changed whenever any important project parameter changes:

- Consortium composition,
- Project duration,
- Change of scope / task
- Project budget and allocation.
- Unforeseen Subcontracting.

Implementation of such changes must follow a specific procedure called: 'Grant Agreement Amendment'. Most changes triggering an amendment to the Grant Agreement relate to updates in the DoA (e.g. changes in tasks and deliverables, changes in efforts allocated, additional partners, etc.). These changes can be relatively minor, in which case they tend to be grouped and implemented together, or they can entail major changes, which might trigger an amendment on their own, especially if it is urgent that the change is officially entered into the contract.

Grant Agreement amendments are submitted to the IHI JU by the Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium. This implies that the Consortium must be aware of and approve any proposed changes before the amendment is requested. The PMO will be responsible for following-up on amendments to the Grant Agreement during the project.

Partners need to contact the PMO office if updates are identified for inclusion in the DoA. The PMO will also communicate the contents of these changes to the ExCom.

The overall procedure for amending the Grant Agreement is described in the document itself. In addition, the internal procedure required prior to the submission of the Amendment request is as follows:

1. The PMO will keep track of all needed amendments requested by the beneficiaries/partners. Meetings and communications with the participants affected will enable to compile all the necessary information to support the changes.
2. The PMO will liaise with the ExCom on this tracking.

3. The PMO will circulate a list of requested changes to the SteerCo for validation and information approval.
4. The PMO will prepare the following documentation:
 - a. A new version of the DoA with the modifications in track changes.
 - b. A first version of a “Request Letter” to be sent to IHI including the changes and their rationale.
 - c. Other documents needed to request the modifications.
5. The SteerCo will receive a copy of the prepared documentation and proceed with a final review.
6. As a final step, the coordinator supported by the PMO will submit, on behalf of the Consortium, the Request Letter, the new version of the DoA and all the additional documentation required by IHI for the changes submitted. The new version of the DoA will also be accessible in the project’s SharePoint.

The Grant Agreement may be affected by other types of minor changes which do not constitute an amendment, but which must be communicated to the Consortium or to the IHI through an information procedure.

In any case, **participants should contact the PMO to confirm the procedure** to follow for any modification needed.

Amendments to the Consortium Agreement may also be necessary during the project, sometimes as a result of changes made to the Grant Agreement amendments. These CA amendments will be handled separately by agreement of all participants, under the coordination of the ExCom and the PMO. The Amendment tracker is available on the project’s shared repository.

3.3 Reports Overview

Part of the contractual obligations are the Periodic (Technical and Financial) reports requested by the IHI, representing the Funding Agency. The purpose of these reports is the assessment of the project progress and generally reviews are carried out by several officers from the IHI and possibly external experts. Financial statements are specific documents in which each participant declares all the costs incurred during each reporting period along with any funding requested to the IHI, when applicable.

The justification of costs is done using an online application tool of the IHI, called “Funding & Tenders Portal”.

In addition to the Financial Statement, IHI-funded participants will be also asked to provide an explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting, and in-kind contributions provided by affiliated entities. Participants receiving IHI funding¹ will also be required to provide an explanation of personnel costs in a use of resources table included below the description of the work carried out by each WP in the technical report.

Specific guidelines for accessing the IHI Reporting tool will be provided by the PMO. These guidelines will include complete instructions and recommendations for adequate reporting. Additionally, webinars will be organised to support staff members with financial responsibilities.

Costs must be entered into the Funding and Tenders Portal system within 60 calendar days after the end of the reporting period together with the use of resources explanation in the cost table. It is wise to prepare in advance for reporting and liaise with any relevant financial or administrative department in your institution, at least one month before the end of the reporting period.

3.3.1 Reportings overview

The reports consist of technical progress reports and financial reports. Both reports are submitted through the EC portal with an exact deadline set out in the GA data sheet. In addition, the consortium will have 2 interim reports, for internal purposes, situated around F2F General Assembly and a Technical review meeting organized by the IHI office.

Type of Report	Month	Scope
1 st Periodic Report	M12	1 st Technical & Financial Report
Interim Report	M20	Interim report (<i>internal</i>)
2 nd Periodic Report	M30	2 nd Technical & Financial Report
Mid-Term Review	M36	Technical progress assessment by the IHI office
Interim Report	M42	Interim report (<i>internal - depending on the project progress</i>)
3 rd Periodic Report	M48	3 rd Technical and Financial Report
4 th and Final Report	M60	Final Technical & Financial Report (Including CFS)

The Technical Report undergoes a quality assurance check by both the PMO and the SteerCo before submission to the IHI. As the reports are the compilation of 12 or 18 months of work, a timely delivery is priority to ensure the review procedure can be carried out appropriately.

Activities: Periodic Report – quality assurance

11

3.3.2 Eligible cost

As a general rule, for costs to be eligible, they must be incurred by the beneficiary during the project's life-time and must be reasonable. More specifically, eligibility criteria are explained in the rules of the Grant Agreement and are allocated and planned in the budget. Please refer to the Annotated Model Grant Agreement (AMGA) for full explanations on eligible costs for the specific categories.

Before subcontracting any services, please reach out to the SYNTHIA Project Management Office, to discuss the appropriate procedure in case the subcontracting was not foreseen in the Grant Agreement.

The main eligible categories are:

- A. Personnel costs
 - A.1 Employees, A.2 Natural persons under direct contract, A.3 Seconded persons
 - A.4 SME owners and natural person beneficiaries
- B. Subcontracting costs
- C. Purchase costs
 - C.1 Travel and subsistence
 - C.2 Equipment
 - C.3 Other goods, works and services
- D. Other cost categories
 - D.2 Internally invoiced goods and services
- E. Indirect costs

3.3.3 Certificates on the Financial Statement

In addition to the periodic reports, the following partners based on their budget are subject to a Certificate on the Financial Statement if the requested EU contribution is \geq EUR 430 000.00. This certificate is generated by an external auditor and the costs for obtaining the certificate are eligible under the conditions set out in the AMGA. The preparation of the CFS requires the timely contracting of an external auditor who certifies the cost statements for the entire project. As this is a labour-intensive requirement, we recommend contracting this auditor at the latest 3 months before the closure of the project.

Entities according to budget expected to submit a Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS)

1. IISLAFE	11. UPM
2. BSC	14. ITTM
3. LUMC	15. I-HD
4. UNIBO	16. ERASMUS
5. MATICAL	17. UNIVIE
08. HUS	18. FRAUNHOFER
09. ICH	

4 Results

Not applicable

5 Discussion

Not applicable

6 Conclusion

This deliverable highlights the management structures and key management processes with the intention to meet the ambitious demand of fulfilling the project objectives, respecting the large and diverse gathering of experts from the data science and clinical field in the SYNTHIA consortium."

As this deliverable has highlighted, the smooth management of the SYNTHIA project is also made possible in part thanks to complementary management tools adapted and implemented (or implemented in the near future) to meet the demands of the project.

With the SYNTHIA project lasting a total of 5 years, it is inevitable that the project will face changes and obstacles that may require adjustments to the decision-making structure and support tools. This flexibility is foreseen within the decision-making structure and processes, with certain bodies (PMO, ExCom and SteerCo) tasked with evaluating the efficiency of this structure on a regular basis against the evolving nature of the project. Thus, this deliverable will remain valid till changes are deemed necessary by those bodies overseeing the efficient functioning of the key management processes as a whole.

7 Repository for primary data

Not applicable